

THREE-DIMENSIONAL FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF FREE EDGE
DELAMINATION OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

A solid hexahedral finite element is used to analyze the free edge delamination of a $[\pm 25/90]_S$ graphite-epoxy rectangular plate subjected to axial tensile strain. The large storage space problem frequently encountered in the modeling of contoured delamination problems is resolved by using the preconditioned conjugate gradient method. The strain energy release rate along the contoured delamination front is calculated using the modified crack closure method. The numerical results show that mode I strain energy release rate G_I is distributed non-uniformly along the delamination front and reaches a maximum value at the free edge of the laminate.

KEYWORDS: Energy Release Rate; Free Edge Delamination; Interlaminar Free Edge Stress; Preconditioned Conjugate Gradient Method; Three-Dimensional Finite Elements.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, the subject of free edge delamination of composite laminates has attracted considerable attention [1]. This is one of the most frequently encountered types of failure in composite materials. It has been pointed out by, among others, Wang [2,3] that the delamination is mainly due to the free edge interlaminar stresses associated with the anisotropic interaction of the laminate layers. Experimental results (see, for example, Refs. 4 and 5) also confirm that the delamination crack tends to grow initially along the free edge, propagate into the interior of the laminate and cause laminate separation and failure. In reality, the delamination front is usually a complicated two-dimensional contour and in that case straightforward two-dimensional finite element model is insufficient. However, a quasi-three-dimensional finite element model used by Wang[4] is proven to be convenient. To carry a step further, a three-dimensional finite element

model is proposed here to understand the delamination problem.

There have been several studies in the literature using three-dimensional finite elements to estimate stresses in the critical region of the laminates [7,8,9,10,11]. Usually, the analysis results in a large, sparse system of equations, which require a vast amount of computer storage space and quite often make the three-dimensional finite element model impractical and possibly formidable.

Of late, preconditioned conjugate gradient methods for the solution of large systems of linear equations encountered in finite element analysis have attracted the attention of the analyst. With this iterative technique, no storage is required for the fill-in elements encountered in the process of stiffness matrix decomposition. For very sparse matrices with large bandwidth, this can lead to significant savings in storage over conventional complete factorization methods.

In this study, interlaminar free edge stress analysis is performed for a $[\pm 25/90]_S$ graphite-epoxy rectangular plate subjected to an axial tensile strain, and then the onset of contoured delamination on the free edge of this laminate plate is studied using a finite element method approach.

2. FORMULATION

A 64 degree-of-freedom solid hexahedral finite element is adopted here to solve the system of equations by the preconditioned conjugate gradient method instead of the conventional direct elimination method as used in [7].

The conjugate gradient method can be described by using the weighted residual concept in association with the equation $Ax = b$ [12,13]. Let the j th iterative value of x , namely x_j be expressed as a combination of linearly independent basis vectors d_j , as

$$x_j = \sum_{i=1}^j \alpha_i d_i = x_{j-1} + \alpha_j d_j \quad (1)$$

where α_j represent some scalar quantities, and the d_j 's are orthogonal to matrix A , i.e.,

$$d_i^T A d_j = \delta_{ij}, \quad (2)$$

δ_{ij} being the Kronecker delta function.

The residual error r_j for the j th iteration can be written as

$$r_j = b - Ax_j = b - Ax_{j-1} - \alpha_j A d_j = r_{j-1} - \alpha_j A d_j \quad (3)$$

premultiplying $d_j^T A$ to both sides of Equation (1) gives

$$\alpha_j = \frac{d_j^T A x_j}{d_j^T A d_j} \quad (4)$$

The j th basis vector, d_j is then constructed by using the combination of the residual vector of the previous iteration and the $j - 1^{\text{th}}$ basis vector, as

$$d_j = r_{j-1} + \beta_j d_{j-1} \quad (5)$$

where the scalar β_j can be determined from the orthogonality condition.

The convergence rate of the conjugate gradient method can be improved by using a symmetric positive definite matrix M , so that we seek to solve the system of equations $M^{-1}Ax = M^{-1}b$ in place of $Ax = b$. If M is close to A then the coefficient matrix $M^{-1}A$ is close to the identity matrix and the solution is obtained. This is the preconditioned conjugate gradient method. The algorithm for this method is briefly outlined below [12]:

$$\text{solve } Mz_{j-1} = r_{j-1} \quad (6)$$

$$\beta_j = z_{j-1}^T r_{j-1} / z_{j-2}^T r_{j-2} \quad (\beta_1 = 0) \quad (7)$$

$$d_j = z_{j-1} + \beta_j d_{j-1} \quad (d_1 = z_0) \quad (8)$$

$$\alpha_j = z_{j-1}^T r_{j-1} / d_j^T A d_j \quad (9)$$

$$x_j = x_{j-1} + \alpha_j d_j \quad (10)$$

$$r_j = r_{j-1} - \alpha_j A d_j \quad (11)$$

3. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

To evaluate the current finite element formulation incorporating the preconditioned conjugate gradient method, a $[\pm 25/90]_S$ graphite-epoxy rectangular laminated plate with and without free edge delamination is chosen for the example study. It would be of interest to apply the current development to study the effect of a different type of delamination on the strain energy release rate. With this in mind, a two-dimensional elliptical crack is assumed in the present work.

3.1 Free edge stress analysis Figure 1(a) shows a $[\pm 25/90]_S$ graphite-epoxy rectangular laminate subjected to a uniform axial strain e_0 in the x -direction. The dimensions of the laminate are assumed as, length = $2a = 60h$, and width = $2b = 30h$, where the ply thickness h equals 0.132 mm. The material properties of the graphite-epoxy are assumed to be those of AS4-3501-06 with $E_x = 145$ GPa; $E_y = E_z = 10.3$ GPa; $G_{xy} = G_{xz} = 6.8$ GPa; $G_{yz} = 3.5$ GPa; $\nu_{xy} = \nu_{xz} = 0.3$; $\nu_{yz} = 0.54$. Two types of finite element model are considered. The first is a half plate model where upper half of the composite laminate is modeled by using 3,120 elements with a total of 54,549 degrees of freedom, see Figure 1 (b). The second is an octant model where only an octant of the composite laminate is

modeled by using 1,560 elements with a total of 27,951 degrees of freedom, see Figure 1(c).

Figure 2 shows the distribution for stress σ_z along the center line at $x/a = 0$ and at $z/h = 0$ for the $[\pm 25/90]_S$ graphite-epoxy laminate as obtained using the half-plate model and the octant model. The normal stress σ_z is seen to be maximum at the free edge and reduced rapidly towards the interior of the laminate. It is seen that the results obtained using the half-plate model agree well with those obtained using a quasi-three-dimensional approach [15]. In the case of the octant model, however, there is some inaccuracy at the interior and this attributes to assumed boundary effects.

Figure 3 shows the stress distribution for σ_z over the middle plane for the $[\pm 25/90]_S$ laminated plate using the half-plate model. From Figure 3, it is seen that the distribution of σ_z on the middle plane exhibits a symmetric trend about the central point of the plate while there are peaks towards the edges. Such peak values are of special interests to the analysts and designers.

Figure 4 shows the stress distribution for σ_{xz} on the middle plane for the $[\pm 25/90]_S$ laminate obtained using a half-plate model. It is observed that the shear stress σ_{xz} is antisymmetric about the central point of the plate.

3.2 Strain Energy Release Rate Analysis Two elliptic type delaminations symmetrical to x-axis, as shown in Figure 5, are modeled to simulate the semicircular localized edge delamination observed during the onset of the delamination process in a $[\pm 25/90]_S$ laminate. For comparison, the material properties of T300/934 graphite-epoxy material system in [14] are used in computation, $E_x = 163.4$ GPa; $E_y = E_z = 11.86$ GPa; $G_{xy} = G_{xz} = 6.48$ GPa; $G_{yz} = 33.45$ GPa; $\nu_{xy} = \nu_{xz} = 0.3$; $\nu_{yz} = 0.54$. The length and width of the plate are 160 mm and 25.4 mm, respectively. The height is taken as $3h$, where h being the thickness of each ply. In this study h is assumed to be 0.132 mm. Figure 6 shows model I, the finite element model for an octant of the plate. It is modeled by 1,260 24-node solid elements for a total of 24,354 degrees of freedom. The element width normal to the delamination front over the whole delamination is taken to be $0.2h$. The circumferential part of the delamination is divided equally into 8 elements of size $0.4h$ each. Figure 7 shows model II, the finite element model for the upper front quarter of the plate covering the entire delamination zone. It is modeled by 2,520 solid elements for a total of 47,718 degrees of freedom. The element dimensions in the region of the crack front are the same as those for the octant.

The first mode strain energy release rate G_I is calculated by the modified crack-closure method [16]. Figure 8 shows the distribution of strain energy release rate G_I over the delamination front. Both the model I for an octant and model II for a quarter of the plate predict the same trend in G_I at either end of the crack front. Towards the middle, however, there is some disagreement. While the quarter-plate model predicts an almost constant G_I in the interior, the octant model predicts that the G_I is nearly as low at the

center of the crack front as it is at the edges. The quasi-three-dimensional solution instead approximates the G_I values to be a constant all over the crack front.

Obviously, the errors caused by using model I for the octant are attributed to the assumed boundary condition at $x = 0$. Comparing the present model II results and those using the quasi-three-dimensional model, it is seen that there is a discrepancy of 12% near $x = \pm 2.5$ mm. This is likely due to differences in the model of the three-dimensional problem between the two methods. The present three-dimensional model, however, generated some interesting distributions of G_I values near the ends of the contoured delamination zone. Obviously, the significantly large values of G_I at the two free-edge corners influence the crack growth pattern.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A three-dimensional solid hexahedral finite element is used to analyze the interlaminar free edge delamination process in composite laminates. The preconditioned conjugate gradient method is adopted to overcome the formidable computer storage space problem encountered in three-dimensional finite element analysis. A two-dimensional contoured delamination in a $[\pm 25/90]_s$ laminate during the initial stages of delamination is studied. The strain energy release rate along the delamination front is calculated, which may provide some insight to the problem of delamination growth.

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Figure 1 Geometry and finite element modeling of a $[\pm 25/90]_s$ graphite-epoxy laminated rectangular plate subjected to an uniform axial strain e_0

Figure 2 The distribution of stress σ_z along a center line at $x/a = 0$ and $z/h = 0$ for the $[\pm 25/90]_S$ graphite-epoxy laminated plate

Figure 3 The distribution of stress σ_z over the middle plane of the $[\pm 25/90]_S$ graphite-epoxy laminated plate (antisymmetric about xz and yz plane)

Figure 4 The distribution of stress σ_{xz} over the middle plane of the $[\pm 25/90]_S$ graphite-epoxy laminated plate

Figure 5 Contoured delamination (not in scale) in the middle plane of the $[\pm 25/90]_S$ graphite-epoxy laminated rectangular plate subjected to an uniform axial strain e_0

Figure 6 Modeling I (a) finite element mesh for a quadrant of the middle plane of the plate (1,260 elements for the octant solid)
 (b) detailed mesh for the corner of delaminated zone

Figure 7 Finite element modeling for the upper front quarter of the plate covering the entire delamination zone (2,520 elements)

Figure 8 Comparison of the distribution of the first mode strain energy release rate G_I